

The Linkage Between the American Economic System and Prolonging Poverty

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Introduction

Before passing the Social Security Act in 1935, Franklin Roosevelt announced to Congress, “The Federal Government must and shall quit this business of relief Continued dependence upon relief induces a spiritual and moral disintegration, fundamentally destructive to the national fiber.” Yet years later, new welfare programs are being signed off on to ‘help’ the general lower class. One fact that needs to be emphasized is that poverty will only be overcome when people are self-supporting. But implementing successful welfare programs convey the impression that it is an impossible task due to the thousands of individuals using the money the government allocates to support them every month. This is where the gaping problem in the welfare system is found- it tends to encourage unproductiveness. There seems to be no reason to go out to put in hard work to bring in a few dollars more than to just take advantage of the welfare system, leading to the incentive not to work. If education systems like trade school were more accessible at no cost, and adults are given the opportunity to achieve a higher paying salary, would that provide the motivation needed for that “incentive” to work?

Content Analysis

The general outlook on policymakers is divided. Liberals seek necessity in creating and funding social services to a new extent, arguing “that current levels are inadequate to sustain a family and should be raised” (Butler, 1996). Conservatives consider the fact that welfare doesn’t promote self-sufficiency, therefore setting stricter eligibility requirements. Higher levels of welfare have some pernicious effects on the poor, in fact, are linked to increasing the longevity of poverty. Because of the perverse incentives created by assistance programs that rewarded individuals “who did not work and parents who did not marry,” the percentage of people who were unable or unwilling to sustain themselves beyond the poverty level was rising. Correlations

can be made with welfare decreasing the amount of single mothers who work and people waiting longer periods in time in between jobs as well. The reason it's so difficult for the government to decide the 'right' amount of money to allocate is they cannot make the assumption that a family would be better off if a parent worked longer hours without understanding the specifics of a job and the requirements of someone's children.

The US has been keeping up a steady all time high compared to 50 years ago with new economic and health security programs. Between the years, 1970 and 2017 progress was the

Government's Anti-Poverty Impact Has Grown

Percent reduction in number of people below poverty line from counting government assistance and taxes

Note: Uses Supplemental Poverty Measure (SPM) and 2019 SPM poverty line adjusted for inflation. Corrects for underreporting of benefits in 2017 from SNAP, Supplemental Security Income, and Temporary Assistance for Needy Families.

Source: CBPP analysis of SPM data from Census Bureau and Columbia Center on Poverty and Social Policy. Corrections for underreported benefits from Dept. of Health and Human Services/Urban Institute Transfer Income Model

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most recognized due to advancements in policy.

Sharon Parrott, President of the Center on Budget and Policy Priorities, explained, "In 1970, economic

security programs reduced the number of people in poverty by just 9 percent; by 2017 that figure had

jumped to 47 percent" (Parrott, 2022). Programs like

Supplemental Security Income (SSI), SNAP, EITC (Earned Income Tax Credit), strengthened assistance

for the elderly, disabled, children living in poverty, and those struggling with food scarcity. But gaps in

security programs like ones found in the Child Tax

Credit are plagued by something called an

"upside-down" design, where help doesn't get dished out to those in need most. This 'design' doesn't allow families' with incomes too low to receive credit.

One of the main reasons people will decide to stay under the line of poverty is due to the "cliff effect." When a person makes under a certain amount of money, they don't have to pay for

insurance, high taxes, and they can receive money for food and child support. If they begin to make significantly any more money, all benefits are lost. Individuals having to pay for all of those provided for accommodations, may be driven right back into poverty. As a result, Leah Hamilton, an Associate Professor of Social Work at Appalachian State University says, “many parents turn down promotional opportunities because they would be ultimately worse off financially” (Hamilton, 2018). In addition, unemployed workers usually don’t qualify for insurance since program regulations rarely keep up with changes in the workforce. Restrictive program rules make it impossible for funding to take place as it is at times ‘inadequate.’ People of color and women can’t resource the same options, just because the programs’ were established in the 1930’s, when neither had any rights for jobless benefits.

Welfare recipients are frequently perceived as having their self-esteem and confidence undermined, believing they are unable to support themselves, becoming "self-fulfilling prophecies." Families will stop attempting to assist themselves and accept the fact of spending years on welfare rolls. Social-psychiatrists have started to call this “self-induced dependence.” Stigmatization and getting help when it's not needed are two situations that might give the impression that one is incompetent. According to the findings of two research, even while the majority of AFDC (Aid to Families with Dependent Children) participants do not feel significantly stigmatized by their welfare experience, a considerable number do. In a 1967 survey of AFDC recipients in six Wisconsin counties, 14% of the respondents said that they often felt “embarrassed or uncomfortable” (Handler, 1969).

Encouragement of job training and employment was one of four objectives for welfare reform identified by Congress in 1996, but it ultimately failed. Job training never necessarily promised a job, and more times than not, those who did complete classes would not get hired.

With so many statistics, and varying points of view, and limitations to solutions always present, it is difficult to ‘implement’ real-life solutions; as they have still not been implemented in the first world country, America. It is hard to justify whether a larger fishing net is needed to provide shelter for American families, or if we need to pull back on welfare benefits that way no system of dependence is formed. With the solutions provided, more prerequisites will be instilled on certain programs, yet having realistic advancements in policy that should be a priority on politician's agendas.’

Conclusion

First, when unemployed, an individual must show concrete evidence that they are looking for a job: places they called, resumes submitted, interviews they had, etc. This system would be looked over by coordinators. At the moment, the unemployment system only asks a simple yes or no question: if you are actively looking for a job, which is easy for one to lie about. When an individual does find work, regulations have to be put in place to prevent unstable unemployment. For example, not giving promised amount of hours, and a contract that a worker can not be fired without a good reason or until they find another job.

Secondly, would be to raise the poverty thresholds. People choose to stay in poverty to have access to federal and state programs. Instead of them constantly being in a position of not being able to better themselves or pay for education, the cycle of poverty will remain. New policy adaptations should push towards strengthening trade school and broadening access to free higher educational programs for adults. Individuals who may have not had the chance to go to college for personal or financial issues, is an immigrant, or someone just getting back up on their feet, should be able to get access to a license in a certain field, so they can be able to provide for their families.

To address economic and work insecurity, policymakers must choose the appropriate course of action, and although welfare is only a drop in the bucket to the amount of incentives that need to be executed, this should be everyone's main priority. Educational accessibility represents the foundation of a society; when education is weak among the population, economically the country doesn't do very well. The government needs to stress the investment of skill building through the "workforce development system by making it more affordable to students" (Parrott, 2022). Only then, will people be fully capable and reliable on themselves, and welfare wouldn't have to be such a depressing factor when it comes to rooting a family in poverty for their entire lives.

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